

Case Report of a Patient With Fournier's Gangrene

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ABSTRACT

Fournier's gangrene is a life-threatening necrotizing fasciitis affecting the soft tissues of the perineal, genital, and perianal regions. It progresses rapidly due to microvascular thrombosis and extensive tissue necrosis. The condition occurs more frequently in men and is associated with comorbidities such as diabetes mellitus, alcoholism, immunosuppression, obesity, and chronic kidney disease. Its polymicrobial etiology, involving both aerobic and anaerobic bacteria, promotes tissue destruction and sepsis. Management requires a multidisciplinary approach including hemodynamic resuscitation, broad-spectrum antibiotic therapy, and aggressive repeated surgical debridement.

KEYWORDS: Fournier's gangrene, sepsis, diabetes mellitus

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INTRODUCTION

Fournier's gangrene is a rapidly progressive necrotizing infection involving the soft tissues of the perineal, genital, and perianal regions. It is considered a surgical emergency due to its high morbidity and mortality rates and its rapid progression to sepsis and multiple organ failure. Originally described by Jean Alfred Fournier in 1883 as an idiopathic gangrene of the penis and scrotum in young men, it is currently recognized as a polymicrobial disease associated with multiple predisposing factors, including diabetes mellitus, obesity, alcoholism, immunosuppression, and chronic kidney disease (1).

The pathophysiology involves synergistic aerobic and anaerobic bacterial infections that induce thrombosis of small subcutaneous vessels, resulting in tissue hypoxia and extensive fascial necrosis. Clinically, patients typically present with severe pain, edema, erythema, and fever, which may rapidly progress to cutaneous necrosis and septic shock if prompt treatment is not initiated (2). Early diagnosis and immediate management with hemodynamic resuscitation, broad-spectrum antibiotics, and surgical debridement constitute the cornerstone of treatment (3).

The purpose of this case report is to describe the clinical presentation, progression, and therapeutic management of a patient with Fournier's gangrene, highlighting the importance of early recognition and a multidisciplinary approach to reduce complications and improve outcomes.

CASE PRESENTATION

A 51-year-old male with a history of long-standing type 2 diabetes mellitus and systemic arterial hypertension, both poorly controlled due to poor treatment adherence, presented to emergency department. He denied any history of allergies. His surgical history was significant for an open cholecystectomy performed seven years earlier.

The current illness began in April 2026 with the appearance of a scrotal lesion that had been present for approximately two weeks. The lesion progressively increased in size and was associated with scrotal swelling and purulent discharge. The patient presented to the emergency department, where a consultation with the General Surgery Department was requested (Figure 1), leading to the diagnosis of Fournier's gangrene.

Upon admission, the patient exhibited signs of systemic inflammatory response syndrome. Laboratory studies revealed a blood glucose level of 431 mg/dL, urea of 49 mg/dL, creatinine of 0.61 mg/dL, leukocyte count of 21,300/ μ L, hemoglobin of 12.6 g/dL, platelet count of 56,000/ μ L, neutrophil count of 17.4×10^3 / μ L, and glycated hemoglobin (HbA1c) of 14%. Arterial blood gas analysis demonstrated a pH of 7.38 and bicarbonate level of 22 mmol/L.

The patient was taken to the operating room, where surgical irrigation and debridement of necrotic tissue were performed.

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Intraoperative findings included scrotal and perianal necrosis with drainage of approximately 80 mL of purulent exudate. Both testes were preserved (Figure 2).

Figure 1. Clinical appearance of extensive perineoscrotal necrotizing fasciitis at admission, demonstrating soft tissue necrosis and severe local infection.

Figure 2. Initial surgical debridement of Fournier's gangrene showing extensive necrosis involving the scrotal and perianal

Subsequently, comprehensive management was initiated, including metabolic and electrolyte control as well as daily bedside wound care. Due to persistence of the infectious process, a second surgical intervention was performed on 5th hospital day consisting of additional irrigation and

debridement along with cystostomy placement. Intraoperative findings included scrotal necrosis involving the cremasteric muscle, pararectal extension, bulbar urethral injury without evidence of perforation, and abundant purulent material extending into the suprapubic region (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Extensive scrotal necrosis with pararectal extension and suprapubic purulent involvement during second surgical debridement.

Figure 4. Application of negative-pressure wound therapy (VAC) with progressive wound edge approximation.

On 10th hospital day, the patient underwent another surgical debridement. Necrotic scrotal margins and gangrenous tissue

were identified and excised, leaving both testes exposed. A purulent collection in the left inguinal region was drained

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through extension of the surgical wound. Additionally, fibrinopurulent tissue was debrided from the penile shaft. The perineal wound was noted to extend to the anoderm, precluding the use of negative-pressure wound therapy due to the inability to achieve an adequate seal and the risk of obstructing the anal canal.

Consequently, on 13th hospital day a loop colostomy of the descending colon was performed to divert fecal flow, facilitate wound care, and prevent fecal contamination of the wound.

On 18th hospital day, negative-pressure wound therapy (VAC) was initiated, allowing progressive approximation of the wound edges (Figure 4). Subsequently, on 23th hospital

Figure 5. Partial wound closure

Figure 6. Complete wound closure following removal of negative-pressure wound therapy.

DISCUSSION

Fournier's gangrene is a rapidly progressive polymicrobial necrotizing fasciitis involving the perineal, genital, and perianal regions and represents a true surgical emergency because of its high morbidity and mortality rates. The disease most commonly affects men in the fifth and sixth decades of life and is frequently associated with comorbidities that impair immune function, particularly diabetes mellitus.

The patient described in this report fits the classic epidemiological profile, being a 51-year-old man with long-standing type 2 diabetes mellitus and systemic arterial hypertension with poor therapeutic adherence. Significant metabolic derangement was evident, with a blood glucose level of 431 mg/dL and HbA1c of 14%, conditions known to impair leukocyte function, promote microangiopathy, and increase susceptibility to severe infections. Previous studies have reported diabetes mellitus in up to 60% of patients with Fournier's gangrene, and it has been associated with more extensive disease and prolonged hospitalization.

In this case, approximately two weeks elapsed between symptom onset and specialized evaluation, during which progressive scrotal enlargement and purulent drainage developed. Delayed presentation is a major factor associated with disease progression, sepsis, and increased mortality.

day the VAC system was replaced and partial wound closure was performed in two layers using 2-0 Vicryl for the subcutaneous tissue and 2-0 nylon for the skin with tension-relieving sutures (Figure 5).

The patient demonstrated favorable clinical progress, with no evidence of active infection and adequate granulation tissue formation. On 28th hospital day, the negative-pressure wound therapy device was removed and complete wound closure was achieved (Figure 6).

Following satisfactory wound healing, control of the infectious process, and overall clinical stability, the patient was discharged home for outpatient follow-up.

Upon admission, the patient exhibited both clinical and biochemical evidence of systemic inflammatory response, including marked leukocytosis and neutrophilia, findings commonly observed in advanced necrotizing infections.

Early aggressive surgical debridement performed at admission was crucial for initial infection control. However, as reported in contemporary series, a single procedure is rarely sufficient due to the progressive nature of the disease. The need for multiple reinterventions in this patient reflects the characteristic behavior of Fournier's gangrene, in which the extent of devitalized tissue often becomes fully apparent only during clinical evolution. Subsequent procedures revealed extension of necrosis into the perianal tissues, pararectal region, penile shaft, and cremasteric muscle, indicating extensive disease involvement.

A notable feature of this case was the presence of bulbar urethral injury without perforation, which prompted suprapubic urinary diversion through cystostomy. Urinary diversion is a valuable therapeutic option when urethral involvement exists or when contamination of perineal wounds must be minimized. Furthermore, extension of the wound to the anoderm initially prevented the use of negative-pressure wound therapy because an adequate seal could not

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be achieved and there was concern regarding potential obstruction of the anal canal.

The subsequent creation of a loop colostomy represented an appropriate therapeutic decision given the extensive perineal involvement and high risk of fecal contamination. Although fecal diversion remains controversial, several authors recommend its use in patients with significant anorectal involvement, anal sphincter exposure, or inability to maintain local contamination control, circumstances present in this case.

Once the infectious process had been controlled and intestinal diversion established, negative-pressure wound therapy could be successfully implemented. VAC therapy has demonstrated significant benefits in the management of complex soft tissue defects, including reduction of edema, stimulation of angiogenesis, accelerated granulation tissue formation, and decreased bacterial burden. The favorable response observed after VAC placement allowed progressive wound closure and definitive healing without the need for more complex reconstructive procedures.

Preservation of both testes throughout the infectious process is consistent with previous reports, as testicular involvement is uncommon because testicular arterial supply arises directly from the abdominal aorta and generally remains unaffected even in the presence of extensive scrotal necrosis.

Finally, the successful clinical outcome and hospital discharge without evidence of active infection underscore the importance of a multidisciplinary approach involving early diagnosis, strict metabolic control, broad-spectrum antibiotic therapy, serial debridement, urinary and fecal diversion when indicated, and the use of negative-pressure wound therapy to optimize wound healing. This case illustrates how the combination of these strategies can significantly improve outcomes in patients with extensive and potentially fatal Fournier's gangrene.

CONCLUSION

Fournier's gangrene remains a potentially lethal condition requiring early diagnosis and immediate surgical intervention. This case demonstrates how severe metabolic dysregulation associated with diabetes mellitus may

contribute to the rapid progression of infection and extensive perineogenital tissue destruction.

Despite the severity of the disease and the need for multiple surgical debridements, the combination of intensive metabolic control, urinary and fecal diversion, negative-pressure wound therapy, and staged surgical management successfully controlled the infection, preserved both testes, and achieved definitive wound closure. These findings reinforce the importance of an aggressive multidisciplinary approach to optimize clinical outcomes in patients with extensive Fournier's gangrene.

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